

“A Study on the Role of Social Media in Attracting Customers”

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Abstract

Social media has become a way of life. A large mass of people use social media to keep in touch with their loved ones; however, these days a growing number of businesses are also using them for endorsement of their products. Many types of social media tools are available which businesses can utilize to attain various goals such as brand promotion, brand management, image building, lead generation, etc. There is lots of reason as to why a certain company needs social media marketing. Social media such as LinkedIn, Facebook, and Twitter are fundamentally changing how consumers communicate with each other and evaluate product information. In this course, the paper discusses the implications of the rapid advent of social media in respect to effectively managing businesses. For new business ventures, carefully articulating the role of social media is going to be a critical component in defining their business vision and strategic plan moving forward. For established organizations, understanding and embracing social media will ensure that they are not blindsided by disorderly changes in the marketplace, and guide their efforts at sustaining market leadership in the future. The objective of this study is to find out how the social media outline the market place situation and the marketing strategies and programmers that would help the company achieved its business and organization goals. The paper carries out empirical research to understand the effectiveness of social media as a marketing tool and an effort has been made to analyze the extent social media helps consumers in buying decision making. Various statistical tests have been applied to support the research hypothesis. The present paper tries to find out how companies are integrating social media into marketing so as to boost awareness and generate excitement about their products. The paper comes with an outcome that if used well social media can help businesses build essential emotional connections with people, thereby creating a profound impact both on customers and employees. Consumers can become partners, helping to tell the brand story and co-creating products and services that ultimately drive bottom line success.

Key Words: Social Media, Customers, Marketing, Networking.

INTRODUCTION

In a short span of time, social media has become one of the most loved mediums for the Indian youths today. Due to the increasing use of social media, the way organizations communicate with their stakeholders is changing and it becomes increasingly important for organizations to be aware of social media and what it could mean for an organization. Social Media Marketing is the most recent new marketing concept and every business owner wants to identify how social media can generate worth for their business. People are social by nature and collect or share information that is important to them. Social Media Marketing is about understanding how technology is making it easier for people to connect socially with their social networks and how business can make profit from that understanding. More and more of customers, whether for personal use, business-to-consumer or business-to-business reasons use social media in every aspect of their daily life. There is a common misconception that social media and social networking sites are two synonymous terms. Social media are tools for sharing and discussing information. It is a kind of online media which encourages every member for feedback and contribution. It is a social mechanism of two way communication facilitating the sharing of information between users within a defined network via web 2.0. It involves online activities in which the user contributes to content creation. This media motivates user participation which can be as simple as posting comments or giving votes or as complex as recommending content to other user on the basis of preferences of people with similar interests and lifestyle. Thus social media can be described as a broad term inclusive of activities where people create content, share it, bookmark it and network at a phenomenal rate. On the other hand social networking sites are a place where in one forms communities of concern to connect to others. Social networking sites exploit social media technology to join with people and build relationships. Social networking sites allow individuals to create their profile within a bounded system, share with other users and view and pass through their list of connections and those made by others within the system (Boyd & Ellison, 2007). It can be thus concluded that social networking sites are a form of social media. Sites like Face book, Twitter, LinkedIn, Orkut are influencing the way users establish, maintain and cultivate a range of social relationships, from close friendships to casual acquaintances. Consumers today want to be more informed about products before they make the purchase. Most importantly, social networks are extremely capable of informing and influencing

purchase decisions, as many users now trust their peer opinions more than the marketing strategists. Customers now have the power to talk back at the brand and broadcast their opinions of the brand. Therefore, marketers have no choice but to treat them differently and with greater respect.

The world's internet-using population has crossed a billion, with Asia accounting for 45% of it. There has been an extraordinary 600% growth of internet users in Asia since the year 2000. Asia's two largest economies, China and India already boast of 500 million internet users, anticipated to go up to 1200 million users by 2015. Given the fact that internet dissemination in Asia is below 30% at present, this means explosive potential growth in Asia's emerging markets. The Internet, and through it, social media is leading major evolutionary trends both in society and business. Values, culture, norms, and behavior are making paradigm shifts. Understanding these shifts requires careful deliberation of factors that are forcing the digital revolution. The internet and its increasing use by populations worldwide and the rising influence of social networks are redefining the way people connect with each other. This can be perceived strongly in the changing norms and values of digital natives. Social media is flawlessly integrated into the lives of millions of people through their cell phones and computers, defining the way they communicate, socialize, conduct business and explore the world.

REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

Research has acknowledged that social media could be valuable and essential for companies and that especially social networking sites, such as Facebook and LinkedIn, could be used for the communication with customers and suppliers, for relationship and trust building and for identifying potential partners (Howe, 2006; Piller, et al., 2012). Furthermore, social media can also be used to increase traffic to the corporate website, disseminate significant information, attract new customers, gain feedback, fostering customer relationships, and establish a two-way conversation, which provide the marketers some help with getting insight in the preferences and the loyalty of the buyers and promoting the brand identity (Howe, 2006). Additionally, social media can be used for generating value for their brand by means of information, knowledge, conversations, relationships and e-commerce (Prahalad & Ramaswamy, 2004). Due to social media, organizations get their customers better to know by means of collecting more information on their customer. In addition, organizations are now able to have an own back office or customer relationship management system where all the data and information of the customers

are stored (Pralhad & Ramaswamy, 2004). Due to social media, businesses can easily communicate with potential stakeholders, such as suppliers and customers in a more efficient way which can improve the relationships between them (Erdoğan & Çiçek, 2012). Furthermore, Nair and Sidhu (2009) found that social media can play a role in identifying and gaining new leads for organizations. With the help of social media, businesses have the ability to monitor online conversations which can help them to identify trends and needs and subsequently, organizations can then early discover some business opportunities before the competitors do. Marketers are also interested in the way that social media can easily create free word of mouth. Word of mouth is important; Li and Bernoff (2008, 132) state that 83% of people trust information from a friend that has used the product, while only 63% trust the information that comes from a known expert and in the internet word of mouth can grow to exponential numbers if compared to traditional settings. Sterne (2001, 312) claims that 57% of people would go to an internet site that was recommended by a friend and Jim Stengel, marketing director of Procter & Gamble, has also mentioned that people trust even the anonymous people on forums more than advertisements (Salmenkivi & Nyman 2007, 97). Even the world of B2B marketing has changed; vast majority of business buyers are relying on word of mouth when making decisions (Bush 2009, 5).

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The present paper aims to achieve the following objectives:

- 1) To find out how the social media outline the market place situation and the marketing strategies and programmers.
- 2) To understand the effectiveness of social media as a marketing tool
- 3) To analyze the extent social media helps consumers in buying decision making.
- 4) To study the use and utility of social media among people and business managers.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Type	: Empirical
Type of Sampling	: Convenience Sampling
Sampling Unit	: Individual persons and Businessmen
Sampling Universe	: District Moradabad, Uttar Pradesh
Sample size	: 100 Individual persons and Businessmen
Data Type	: Primary as well as Secondary Data

Data Source : Survey through questionnaire and review of literature.

Scope of the study : The scope of study is related to persons who are engaged in social media in District Moradabad, Uttar Pradesh. The scope of the research shall be in reliance with the methods and instruments of research used in this study. Special attention has been given to carry out the research in a manner such that it contributes to the overall study of importance of social media in attracting the customers.

The paper is not confined to any particular area; on the other hand it is applicable to whole India. However, opinion of various businessmen and entrepreneurs in Moradabad district of Uttar Pradesh has been taken about the pros, cons and issues of social media. Their views have been incorporated in this paper. The paper also takes the references of various articles written by various experts on importance of social media.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Questions were asked from the respondents about the utility and use of social media. We get the following data:

Table 1

S. No.	Variables	Responses	No. of Respondents	Total
1.	Age	10-20	4	100
		20-30	26	
		30-40	33	
		40-50	21	
		50+	16	
2.	Occupation	Student	4	100
		Housewife	24	
		Unemployed	5	
		Service	43	
		Business	20	
		Retired	4	
3.	Use of Internet	Regularly	65	
		As & when required	10	

		May be once in a week	25	100
4.	Extent of knowledge about Social Networking	Basic	30	100
		Average	55	
		Expert	15	
5.	Duration of using social networking sites	0-1 month	0	100
		1-6 months	5	
		6-12 months	10	
		1-2 years	20	
		2-4 years	45	
		4+ years	20	
6.	Social media sites	Facebook	100	All respondents use more than one social media site.
		Linkedin	85	
		Googleplus	66	
		Twitter	37	
		MySpace	25	
		Youtube	100	
		Orkut	10	
		Others	44	
7.	Hours per week spend on social networking sites	0-5	17	100
		6-10	30	
		11-20	28	
		21-30	20	
		31-40	2	
		41-50	2	
		Above 50	1	
8.	Purpose for using social media platform	Connecting with friends	40	
		Exchanging views	45	

		about product and services		
		Playing games and contests	13	
		Others	2	100
8.	Reasons of joining a fan club/group of a brand	To receive tips	80	All respondents have more than one reason
		To get promos	85	
		To hear about events	100	
		Stay up to date	100	
9.	Information included on social networking sites	E mail address	100	All respondents have more than one information to include on sites
		Telephone No.	85	
		Home town/city	100	
		Political views	45	
		Real name	80	
		Photos of yourself	100	
		Photos of others	50	
		Relationship status	75	
10.	No. of friends in all social networking sites	0-50	14	100
		50-100	5	
		100-200	5	
		200-500	66	
		500+	10	
11.	Communication to people on social sites	Close friends	100	All respondents communicate to more than one group of persons
		Co-workers	100	
		Family	100	
		Friends	100	
		People that live far away	100	
		Strangers / people	45	

		already not known		
12.	Write Blogs	Yes	45	100
		No	55	
13.	Information about the product on various social-networking sites persuade to buy the product	Yes	60	100
		No	40	
14.	What is the extent of using of social-media tools in daily work	I don't need it in my work	15	100
		Regularly	65	
		As and when need arises	20	

- 1) The majority age that uses social media sites ranges from 20-40 years. The young generation uses social media sites in great number.
- 2) The majority of respondents that are on social media sites come from service and business class. However, we find that housewives are showing great interest to connect with friends via social media sites. The discussion with them shows that they discuss with their friends about the dresses, ornaments and other daily use items.
- 3) 65 percent of the respondents use social media sites on regular basis. 58 percent sit on the internet for 6-20 hours per week.
- 4) Majority of the respondents are using social media sites for more than one year.
- 5) It is clear from the above table that facebook is the most popular social media site. However, all respondents have opened their login id on more than one social media websites.
- 6) 45 percent of the respondents are using social media sites for the purpose of exchanging views about various products and services. 40 percent respondents choose the social media for connecting with the friends.
- 7) All respondents have more than one reason for joining a fan club or group of brand. To remain updates about various promos, offers, events etc are the main reasons.

- 8) All respondents update their e-mail, address, date of birth, home town, etc on sites. Also they upload their photos and their friends' photos on the social media sites.
- 9) 66 percent of the respondents have lots of friends connected (200-500 friends)
- 10) All respondents try to communicate with more than one group of persons such as Close friends, Co-workers, Family members, Friends, People that live far away and Strangers / people not already know.
- 11) 55 percents of the respondents do not write blogs.
- 12) 60 percent of the respondents feel that the information available on the sites about the products persuade them to buy. They are considering social media before starting of buying decision making process.

Questions were asked from the respondents about the security of data and to post their data in spite of security concerns.

1 for Not at all 2 for A Little 3 for Some what high

We get the following data:

Table 2

Variables regarding the social networking site mostly used by respondents	Not at all (1)	A little (2)	Somewhat high (3)	Mean
I feel that the privacy of my personal information is protected	20	50	30	2.10
I trust it will not use my personal information for any other purpose	30	61	9	1.79
I worry that I will be embarrassed by information others post about me on it	12	20	68	2.56
I would continue to use it regardless of its privacy policy if it helps me meet new people	5	5	90	2.85
I would continue to use it	5	4	91	2.86

regardless of its privacy policy if it helps me stay in touch with friends				
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From the above table, it is clear that majority of the respondents do not trust on social media sites regarding the protection of data uploaded. The respondents score on 1-3 scale and we find that they do not trust very high on the social media regarding privacy and use of personal data and therefore, we get the average of 2.10 and 1.79 respectively. But even than they want to continue with these social media sites to get in touch with new people and friends which is depicted from the above table with the average of 2.85 and 2.86.

Questions were asked from the businessmen and persons in-charge of business about the importance and use of social media. We get the following data:

Table 3

S. No.	Variables	Responses	No. of Respondents	Total
1.	Goal of the social media exercise	Create market visibility	100	All respondents have more than one goals
		Create online visibility for brand	100	
		Build credibility	100	
		Get new customers	100	
		Target the right audience	100	
		Create a community	56	
		Drive sales	100	
		Derive feedback	75	
2.	Group of people trying to reach out	New customers	100	All respondents wants to reach out more than
		Existing customers	100	
		Vendors	45	
		Wholesalers	56	
		Others	45	

				one group
3.	Business ready to become social	Yes	85	100
		No	15	
4.	Performed a social media exercise before	Yes	23	100
		No	77	
5.	Social media platforms on which promotion is carried out/going to carry out.	Facebook	100	All respondents wants more than one platform
		Linkedin	100	
		Googleplus	75	
		Twitter	100	
		MySpace	90	
		Youtube	100	
		Orkut	43	
		Others	54	
6.	Identified any business advantage of using social media over traditional media	Yes	90	100
		No	10	
7.	Internet hours per week willing to commit to this promotional exercise	0-5	10	100
		6-10	26	
		11-20	24	
		21-30	15	
		31-40	10	
		41-50	10	
		Above 50	5	
8.	Areas on which exercise influence	Awareness	100	All respondents have more than one area to influence
		Sales	80	
		Royalty	56	

9.	Organization have a dedicated department to manage communication via social media	Yes	20	100
		No	80	
10.	Results expected from this social media promotion exercise	Increase sales	100	All respondents have more than one result expected
		Customer retention	100	
		Brand Building	100	
		Increased market share	100	

- 1) Respondents who are engaged in business have more than one goal for the social media exercise such as Create market visibility, Create online visibility for brand, Build credibility, Get new customers, Target the right audience, Create a community, Drive sales and Derive feedback, etc.
- 2) Respondents under survey wants to reach to more than one group of people such as new customers, existing customers, vendors, wholesalers, etc
- 3) Seeing the importance that social media plays in people’s life 85 percent of the respondents are ready to expose their business to social media sites. They are eager to advertise their products on various social media sites.
- 4) Only 23 percent had already performed the social media exercise before.
- 5) Majority of respondents wants to use more than one social media sites for the promotion of their products with facebook, linkedin, youtube are most popular.
- 6) 90 percent of the respondents have identified the business advantage of using social media sites as compared to traditional media.
- 7) Majority of the respondents (50 percent) committed that they will devote at least 6-20 hours per week for promotional exercise.
- 8) All respondents have more than one area to influence or work upon such as Awareness, Sales, Loyalty, etc.

- 9) 80 percent of the respondents agreed that Organizations to which they belong does not have a dedicated department to manage communication via social media. However, the scene is changing very fast and 90 percent have identified the role of social media in today's business environment.
- 10) All the respondents have agreed that the results expected from the social media promotion exercise are Increase sales, Brand Building, Increased market share, etc.

BENEFITS OF SOCIAL MEDIA

The exponential growth of social media, from blogs, Facebook and Twitter to LinkedIn and YouTube, offers organizations the chance to join a conversation with millions of customers around the globe every day. (HBR)

- 1) One of the major merits of social media marketing is the ability to reach a wide audience by breaking down geographic boundaries. Historically communication with others was limited by geographical boundaries and the current technological of the era. Today's social media technologies enable nearly everyone to reach a global audience for interpersonal interaction and exchanging information.
- 2) It is well-established that people feel more connected with a company when they have direct communication on an ongoing basis and opportunities to express their opinions (Brown 2010)
- 3) Indeed, social networking conversations create a level of immediacy and a kind of public intimacy that is impossible with traditional marketing. And since most large or medium-size companies are perceived by the public as relatively "faceless," social networking gives companies the opportunity to present a human face in the form of a social media spokesperson -- an individual who can nurture person-to-person conversations which builds trust in the company's authenticity as well as its professionalism.
- 4) Unlike traditional face-to-face media, social media allows to communicate with a large number of people in a short span of time, at a few taps on the keyboard. Compared to traditional advertising and marketing, social media is accessible, affordable, immediate and easily altered or updated.
- 5) Although there are no direct costs in using social media, but it will take up a few hours of time of an employee, to monitor and update your social media channels.

- 6) Marketers can't afford to ignore social media because it has become an accepted means of communication by customers who will be sharing information about products and services.

ROLE OF SOCIAL MEDIA IN BUSINESS ORGANISATION

Social media has become a way of life. A large majority of people use social media to keep in touch with their loved ones; however, these days a growing number of businesses are also using them for promotion. There are many types of social media tools available which businesses can utilize to attain various goals such as brand promotion, brand management, image building, lead generation, etc. The innovative mode of communication helps businesses in a variety of ways such as.

- 1) **Targeted Audience:** The biggest challenge in promoting a business online is finding the target audience. Customers can be segmented into demographics, psychographics, geography, behavior, etc. Prior to the Internet and social media sites, it could take businesses years of research and investment to reach their target audience. Now businesses depend on social media to pin point consumers who are looking for their product or service.
- 2) **Variety of Tools:** Unlike generic search engine optimization that provides limited tools to communicate, social media offers a variety of collaboration tools. For example, micro-blogging helps in simultaneously convey the message to masses of people.
- 3) **Cost:** One of the biggest reasons why businesses love to rely on social media tools is cost. For the most part, offline marketing initiatives are costly, but social media campaigns help save a lot of money. Many modern business marketers use the combination of search engine optimization and social media tools to further optimize their online marketing results for a fraction of what they used to pay.
- 4) **Direct Communication:** Many organizations, large and small, are now effectively using social media to directly communicate with their customers. In the same way, customers can also directly communicate with the businesses about their products and services. Social media provides a two-way street for interaction and feedback, enabling immediate and direct communication about products and services.

STRATEGIES FOR SOCIAL MEDIA EXPERT TO ATTRACT THE CUSTOMERS

Today, there are businesses that engage in social media and those that do not. Those at least experimenting with the formidable, yet shifting landscape of intelligence and communication are learning how to adapt and connect in a new world of conversation, networking, and influence. Those that have yet to evaluate the opportunities and advantages for socialized marketing, service, sales, and branding will find it increasingly difficult to learn, adapt, and magnetize customers, prospects as well as their influencers.

We present few strategies such as:

- 1) Work closely with existing marketing staff to understand your marketing strategy and goals.
- 2) Research the most appropriate social media channels for your business.
- 3) Help to set up own accounts.
- 4) Determine with the best tools to manage those accounts.
- 5) Train internal staff how to manage those accounts using the tools.
- 6) Develop metrics and institute tracking devices to gauge return on investment.
- 7) Advise on how to deliver promotional content and campaigns through the channels.
- 8) Monitor changes in social media technology, channels, and tools and make adjustments and provide training.

SUGGESTIONS

- 1) More than 60 percent of users are always considering social media networks at the time of getting into purchase decision. Therefore, it is important for the marketers to upload information on the social sites where there is huge probability to come into the eyes of customers and if successes into pursuing the customers' then positive word of mouths will automatically get started. This will sooner or later gives rise to multiple impacts and conversation will get started on the web.
- 2) 45 percent of the respondents are using social media sites for the purpose of exchanging views about various products and services so, here marketers have plenty of opportunity to communicate with their targets and offer them their products/service to persuade them to transact and become loyal customer for them. It is a fast growing platform for brands in all the sectors. It acts as an effective tool as it is the best way to reach out market segment without incurring huge cost.

- 3) 58 percent sit on the internet for 6-20 hours per week. It is clear that how much it is important for the marketers to exploit the situation by making workable marketing strategies.
- 4) One of the keys to a successful social media marketing platform knows your own business. A large corporation is going to have needs and attributes which require a very different approach to social media marketing than a small, local business will need to be successful. If it is a larger company there is a need to focus on using social media to connect with a larger audience in order to get national exposure for your brand and products. If it is a small, local business social media should be used to build a dedicated, loyal customer base by offering the personal touch that only a local business can provide. If business has a product or service that is primarily used or purchased by other businesses, social media should be used to network with other businesses in order to increase the visibility in the commercial marketplace. If business offers a product or service which is primarily used or purchased by individual consumers, social media should be used as a way to develop a pool of customers who see your brand as quality, hip, and available. No matter the size or nature of business, a knowledge of company's strengths, target market, and product or service niche is an essential part of any successful social media marketing platform.
- 5) Lastly, if it is within company's financial position to do so, consider creating a position specially designed to create, develop, and maintain company's social media marketing presence. More and more colleges are offering degrees specifically tailored to social media marketing, and graduates of these programs are trained and ready to help utilize the powerful marketing tools social media offers to increase the exposure of brand and the sales. If company is not able to afford a dedicated in house position for social media management, hire a third-party service provider that specializes in social media marketing.

CONCLUSION

If used well social media can help businesses build essential emotional connections with people, thereby creating a profound impact both on customers and employees. Consumers can become partners, helping to tell the brand story and co-creating products and services that ultimately drive bottom line success. Partners and employees feel empowered, adding to company morale

and investment portfolio. The social media area is changing rapidly as services fall in and out of favour with users. It is best to keep up-to-date with the new sites, especially the ones your customers may be switching to. There is a global trend towards accessing social media from mobile devices, rather than desktops, and this is likely to increase.

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